

EFFECT OF CFRP ON VORTEX-INDUCED VIBRATION OF A BRIMMED-DIFFUSER SHROUD FOR A WIND TURBINE

Taeyoung Kim¹, Hiroto Nagai², Nobuhide Uda³ and Yuji Ohya⁴

¹ Aeronautics and Astronautics, Kyushu University, Fukuoka, Japan, kim-ty@aero.kyushu-u.ac.jp,

<http://www.aero.kyushu-u.ac.jp/assl/>

² Aeronautics and Astronautics, Kyushu University, Fukuoka, Japan, nagai@aero.kyushu-u.ac.jp,

<http://www.aero.kyushu-u.ac.jp/svl/>

³ Aeronautics and Astronautics, Kyushu University, Fukuoka, Japan, uda@aero.kyushu-u.ac.jp,

<http://www.aero.kyushu-u.ac.jp/assl/>

⁴ Research Institute for Applied Mechanics, Kyushu University, Kasuga, Japan, ohya@riam.kyushu-u.ac.jp, <https://www.riam.kyushu-u.ac.jp/>

Keywords: Wind-lens, CFRP, Vortex-induced vibration, Aeroelastic analysis

ABSTRACT

A brimmed-diffuser shroud for a wind turbine is a ring-like short duct installed around a rotor. It is also called a wind-lens because its shape is designed to gather and accelerate wind passing through the rotor to enhance the power generation efficiency of the wind turbine. This effect results from vortex shedding that is intentionally generated by the brim. However, the periodical vortex shedding can induce a vibration in the thin structure of the wind-lens mostly made of aluminum alloy. Besides, this vortex-induced vibration possibly harms the wind-lens structure in the case where resonance occurs due to the coincidence between the vortex frequency and the natural frequency. In order to prevent the wind-lens from the resonance, the modal characteristics of the wind-lens need to be improved, which are related to the stiffness and mass distribution of its structure. This study conducted a numerical aeroelastic analysis using both three-dimensional FEM (Finite Element Method) and two-dimensional CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) for the wind-lens structure to simulate the vortex-induced vibration. The analytic models are the wind-lens whose material is replaced with a CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic) laminate, and they were compared to the original model made of aluminum alloy. The result showed that the CFRP laminate used for the wind-lens structure is valid for the change of the vibrational modes and an increase in the natural frequencies. Nevertheless, the overall displacement amplitude of the vortex-induced vibration did not reduce. It is because the replacement of CFRP on the diffuser is not much effective on the vibrational characteristics of the most susceptible vibrational mode to the vortex shedding, i.e., rotation of the cross-section even though it improves the vibrational characteristics of the other modes.

1 INTRODUCTION

A brimmed-diffuser shroud, also known as a wind-lens, is used for the amplification of the power output from a wind turbine [1]. As shown in Fig. 1, it features a brim at the outlet of the diffuser. Its role is to gather wind at the inlet and to form vortices at the outlet, which then lower the air pressure behind the diffuser. Because of the pressure difference, the wind gathered at the inlet of the diffuser is drawn, being accelerated, and the rotor rotates faster. Since the power output is proportional to wind speed cubed, a small increase in wind speed can contribute to improving the power output from the wind turbine. For this reason, the brimmed-diffuser shroud enables a wind power generation system to operate even at areas where the wind is relatively weak [2]. Despite its advantages, a large-amplitude vibration in a brimmed-diffuser shroud by the vortex shedding was observed at a moment when the maximum instantaneous wind speed of 19.5 m/s was recorded in 2012 [3]. This type of flow-induced vibration generally matters in a variety of structures, such as tall buildings and large bridges [4]. Accordingly, the vortex-induced vibration has been researched for common cross-sections in civil engineering, such as circular cylinders [5], rectangular prisms [6], triangular prisms [7], H-beams [8], and octagonal beams [9]. Our previous study conducted a numerical simulation for the vortex-induced

vibration for the brimmed-diffuser shroud. The numerical result was in good agreement with the actual vortex-induced vibration that we observed at that time. We found that the supporting structures are required to be strengthened as well as the diffuser to improve the vibrational characteristics [10]. One of the methods is the use of CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic). Since a CFRP composite possesses low density, high stiffness, and high damping capacity [11], in the aerospace industry, it is used to avoid wing flutter by modifying the mode shapes and the natural frequencies [12]. In the same manner, it is expected that the vortex-induced vibration can be lessened by replacing the current metallic material with CFRP in the structure of the brimmed-diffuser shroud. Thus, this study investigates the effect of the application of CFRP to the brimmed-diffuser shroud on the vortex-induced vibration, using a numerical aeroelastic analysis coupling three-dimensional modal analysis by FEM (Finite Element Method) and two-dimensional CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics).

Figure 1: A wind power generator with a brimmed-diffuser shroud

2 STRUCTURAL MODEL

2.1 The Original Wind-Lens Model

Figure 2: The schematic of the cross-section of the brimmed-diffuser shroud and its dimensions

The object of this study is a brimmed-diffuser shroud for 3 kW wind power generators that experienced the vortex-induced vibration. Figure 2 illustrates its cross-section with the dimensions. This model is named C_{ii}B10, where C_{ii} indicates one of the cycloidal cross-sectional shapes for a wind-lens and B10 means that the height of the brim is 10% of the throat diameter. The material of the shroud is Al6061 ($E = 68.8 \text{ GPa}$, $\rho = 2700 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $\nu = 0.33$), and its thickness is 1 mm. It is supported by 1143 mm long five arms made of the same aluminum alloy, which are a rectangular hollow beam (outer 89 x 35 mm, inner 60 x 25 mm). They are located 300 mm apart from the inlet of the shroud,

fixed to the nacelle. The beam member, named a diffuser-stay, to connect the support arm to the shroud is made of SS400 ($E = 206 \text{ GPa}$, $\rho = 7900 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $\nu = 0.3$), and the dimension of the cross-section is $55 \times 7.765 \text{ mm}$. Additionally, this structure includes five ribs made of the same steel in the shroud and two-lined corrugation on the brim, as shown in Fig. 3. They prevent the shroud and the brim from being bent by wind load. For convenience, the model explained above is referred to as the original model.

Figure 3: The aluminum alloy diffuser model for the analysis

2.2 The CFRP Wind-Lens Models

Figure 4: The CFRP diffuser model for the analysis

Wind-lens model (Nomenclature)	The material of the diffuser	The material of the support arms	The ribs & The corrugation
Original model (WL-O)	Aluminum alloy	Aluminum alloy	Present
CFRP diffuser model (WL-D)	CFRP laminate	Aluminum alloy	Absent
CFRP support arm model (WL-S)	Aluminum alloy	Unidirectional CFRP	Present
CFRP in both parts (WL-DS)	CFRP laminate	Unidirectional CFRP	Absent

Table 1: Wind lens models

Instead of aluminum alloy, CFRP ($E_{11} = 130 \text{ GPa}$, $E_{22} = E_{33} = 6 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 4 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{23} = 2.3 \text{ GPa}$, $\rho = 1600 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = 0.33$) is used for the shroud and the support arms. For comparison, three types of the wind-lens model with CFRP are made, as tabulated in Table 1. In the models with the CFRP diffuser, the rib and the two-lined corrugation are removed, as shown in Fig. 4, because these supplementary structures installed for the thin aluminum alloy diffuser are surplus to the CFRP diffuser models that are thicker and stiffer than the aluminum alloy diffuser models. The stacking sequence of the brimmed-diffuser shroud is $[0/60/-60]_{2s}$ with 0.2 mm thick plies where the 0 -degree direction is along the cross-section of the diffuser from the inlet to the brim tip, and the 90 -degree direction corresponds with the circumferential direction. Therefore, the thickness of the CFRP diffuser is 2.4 mm . The weight of the CFRP shroud is almost the same as the sum of the weight of the shroud and the five ribs in the aluminum alloy diffuser model. The bending rigidity is $80.76 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}$,

based on the classical laminate theory [13]. This value is around 14 times the bending rigidity of the 1 mm thick aluminum alloy plate, which is 5.74 N·m. In the support arms, unidirectional CFRP is applied lengthwise with no change in the dimensions of them.

3 NUMERICAL METHOD

The vortex-induced vibration in the brimmed-diffuser shroud is the coupling between the elasticity of the structure and the vortex shedding. In order to analyze this phenomenon, two types of numerical methods are required.

3.1 Three-Dimensional Modal Analysis

Three-dimensional modal analysis was conducted by using a commercial FEM software, ANSYS 19.2, to find the vibrational modes and the natural frequencies of the brimmed-diffuser shroud. As shown in Fig. 5, the boundary condition is the fixed five points at the bottom of each support arm. The elements are 4-node shell type except for the support arms that consist of 2-node beam elements. The total number of elements for the original model was 192,565, and that of the CFRP wind-lens models was 183,880 because of the absence of the ribs. In this analysis, the first four modes are calculated for all models. Then, a cross-sectional mode shape in each mode is extracted on the reference plane which is placed at the location where the maximum displacement appears in the three-dimensional mode shape, as depicted in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: The boundary condition of the analysis model and an example of the reference cross-section

3.2 Two-Dimensional Aeroelastic Analysis

The two-dimensional aeroelastic analysis simulates the vortex-induced vibration by coupling the vibrational characteristics and the aerodynamic forces so that the fundamental mechanism of the vortex-induced vibration in the brimmed-diffuser shroud can be clarified. In this research, a CFD program developed by Nagai et al. [14,15] was employed for the analysis. This program is composed of a two-dimensional Navier-Stokes code coupled with the equation of motion for the structural model. The cross-sectional mode shapes obtained from the three-dimensional modal analysis are the inputs for the CFD program. Based on the theory of the mode superposition, the displacement vector d_i on a cross-sectional mode shape is expressed as follows.

$$d_i(\xi, t) = \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{ik}(\xi) q_k(t) \quad (i=1, 2) \quad (1)$$

In the equation above, t is time, ξ is the curvature coordinate along the cross-section, q_k is the generalized coordinate of k -th mode, and Φ_{ik} is the k -th mode shapes in the i -th coordinate direction on the reference plane. N is the number of modes, which is four in this study. Lagrange's equations of

motion for the k -th mode is

$$M_k(\ddot{q}_k + g_k \omega_k \dot{q}_k + \omega_k^2 q_k) = \int_{L.E.}^{T.E.} \Phi_{ik}(\xi) \cdot \Delta P_i(\xi, t) d\xi \quad (2)$$

where M_k is the generalized mass, g_k is the modal damping coefficient ($= 0.01$), ω_k is the natural frequency, and ΔP_i is the pressure difference vector acting on the cross-sectional mode shape. The right-hand side is integrated from the leading edge to the trailing edge while ΔP_i is computed at each time step using the 2D Navier-Stokes code which does not include a turbulence model. Equation (2) calculates the generalized coordinate at each time step. Then, the displacement of the cross-section is calculated through the superposition of four modes.

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Mode Shapes

All cross-sectional mode shapes were able to be classified into fundamental five modes: radial mode, rotational mode, horizontal mode, brim-bending mode, and camber-bending mode as below.

Figure 6: 3D radial mode (left) and its cross-sectional mode shape (right)

Figure 7: 3D rotational mode (left) and its cross-sectional mode shape (right)

Figure 8: 3D horizontal mode (left) and its cross-sectional mode shape (right)

Figure 9: 3D brim-bending mode (left) and its cross-sectional mode shape (right)

Figure 10: 3D camber-bending mode (left) and its cross-sectional mode shape (right)

The mode shape in Fig. 6 is the oscillation in the radial direction accompanied by the movement of the support arms with little deformation of the shroud. Figure 7 shows the rotational motion. It is also involved in the movement of the support arms, but its pattern is different from the radial mode. The neighboring support arms are moving in opposite directions each other as the neighboring diffuser-stays are pivoting. That results in the rotation of the cross-sectional part in the middle. In the horizontal mode shown in Fig. 8, the support arms together move in the horizontal direction. The three mode shapes above have the movement of the support arms in common. The brim-bending mode in Fig. 9 shows a distinct, simple brim bending. The camber-bending mode in Fig. 10 shows a bending along the chord line from the inlet to the brim tip. The brim-bending mode and the camber-bending modes do not always accompany the oscillation of the support arms, unlike the other mode shapes. The cross-sectional mode shapes and the natural frequencies for the wind-lens models are tabulated in Table 2.

Model	The first mode	The second mode	The third mode	The fourth mode
WL-O	10.92 Hz Radial	11.58 Hz Rotational	20.85 Hz Camber bending + Horizontal	23.64 Hz Horizontal
WL-D	12.46 Hz Radial + Camber bending	12.85 Hz Rotational	21.64 Hz Brim bending	22.57 Hz Camber bending
WL-S	11.90 Hz Radial	12.29 Hz Rotational	24.93 Hz Brim bending + Horizontal	28.50 Hz Brim bending + Horizontal
WL-DS	13.51 Hz Rotational	13.89 Hz Radial + Camber bending	22.69 Hz Camber bending	24.30 Hz Brim bending

Table 2: The natural frequencies and the description of their mode for the wind-lens models

Table 2 shows that there are changes in the mode shapes in WL-D and WL-DS with the CFRP laminate diffuser, compared to WL-O. These two models include the camber-bending in the low orders. It is because of the absence of the ribs to prevent the deformation of the diffuser. In the case of WL-S whose diffuser structure is the same with WL-O, its overall mode shapes resemble those of the original model, and its third and fourth natural frequencies are highest respectively among all models. In WL-DS, the increase in the first and the second natural frequencies is regarded as the effect of the CFRP in the diffuser and the support arms. Most of all, the rotational mode appears in the first mode of WL-DS, unlike the other models. The reason is that the torsional stiffness of the support arms has become relatively weaker, and their oscillation results in the rotational mode, as shown in Fig. 11. For all models, the radial and rotational modes that result from the oscillation of the support arms mainly appear in the first and the second mode, which implies that the support arms are comparatively flexible. It is clear that strengthening them with CFRP raises the natural frequencies, and the mode shapes change in the CFRP diffuser models.

Figure 11: Torsion of the support arms in the first mode of WL-DS

4.2 Estimation of Critical Wind Speed

The vortex shedding behind the brim applies a time-varied load to the shroud periodically. When the vortex frequency corresponds to the natural frequency, resonance in the structure possibly occurs. At this point, a wind speed at which the resonance appears is defined as the critical wind speed. It is possible to estimate the critical wind speed because the vortex frequency is linearly related to wind speed and it is expressed as

$$St = f_{\omega} L / U_0 \quad (3)$$

where St is a Strouhal number which is a non-dimensional variable, f_{ω} is the vortex frequency, L is the reference length, which is the height from the throat to the brim tip, and U_0 is the wind speed. Accordingly, once a Strouhal number is determined, the vortex frequency can be calculated at certain wind speed. In order to find the Strouhal number, the vortices around the rigid diffuser were investigated through the two-dimensional CFD.

Figure 12: Vortex shedding behind the rigid diffuser model at a wind speed of 10 m/s (left) and the time history of the lift and drag coefficients (right)

Figure 12 shows the vortices are shedding from the brim tip and the inside of the brimmed-diffuser shroud when the 10 m/s steady flow is blown from the left. At this moment, the lift force is acting downward, and the drag force is acting horizontally. As the vortices are shedding, the lift and drag forces form high harmonic waves, as shown in the right graph of Fig. 12. Their frequency spectrum can be extracted by using FFT (Fast Fourier Transform). Figure. 13 indicates that the strongest vortex, which is the first vortex-shedding mode, is dominantly related to the lift force, and the other vortex-shedding modes whose frequency is integer multiples of the first vortex frequency are mainly involved in the drag force. The first Strouhal number (St_1) for the first vortex frequency was found to be 0.146. The second one (St_2) is 0.292, which is the doubled value of St_1 , and the third one (St_3) is 0.438.

Figure 13: Vortex spectrum extracted from the time history of the lift and drag coefficients

By comparing the natural frequencies obtained in the modal analysis with the vortex frequencies calculated by the Strouhal numbers, the critical wind speed can be predicted. Figure 14 shows the three vortex frequencies to wind speed and the three natural frequencies of the original model. The intersections between the vortex frequencies and the natural frequencies are the estimated critical wind speeds at which the resonance is likely to occur. In this graph, the second (f_2) and third vortex frequencies (f_3) meet the first and second natural frequencies. Nevertheless, the resonance does not

always occur at the critical wind speed estimated, depending on the relationship between the vibrational modes and the vortex-shedding patterns. Also, the higher order vortex modes do not have enough vortex intensity to excite a vibrational mode. The first vortex mode has the highest vortex intensity, but there are no intersections within a wind speed of 20 m/s due to its low vortex frequency. The estimated critical wind speeds for the wind-lens models are summarized in Tables 3-5.

Figure 14: The estimation of the critical wind speeds for WL-O

Wind-lens model	1st mode	2nd mode	3rd mode	4th mode
WL-O	32.3 m/s	34.2 m/s	61.7 m/s	69.9 m/s
WL-D	36.9 m/s	38.0 m/s	64.0 m/s	66.8 m/s
WL-S	35.2 m/s	36.4 m/s	73.7 m/s	84.3 m/s
WL-DS	40.0 m/s	41.1 m/s	67.1 m/s	71.9 m/s

Table 3: Critical wind speed estimated by the first vortex frequency, f_1 ($St_1=0.146$)

Wind-lens model	1st mode	2nd mode	3rd mode	4th mode
WL-O	16.2 m/s	17.1 m/s	30.8 m/s	35.0 m/s
WL-D	18.4 m/s	19.0 m/s	32.0 m/s	33.4 m/s
WL-S	17.6 m/s	18.2 m/s	36.9 m/s	42.2 m/s
WL-DS	20.0 m/s	20.5 m/s	33.6 m/s	35.9 m/s

Table 4: Critical wind speed estimated by the second vortex frequency, f_2 ($St_2=0.292$)

Wind-lens model	1st mode	2nd mode	3rd mode	4th mode
WL-O	10.8 m/s	11.4 m/s	20.6 m/s	23.3 m/s
WL-D	12.3 m/s	12.7 m/s	21.3 m/s	22.3 m/s
WL-S	11.7 m/s	12.1 m/s	24.6 m/s	28.1 m/s
WL-DS	13.3 m/s	13.7 m/s	22.4 m/s	24.0 m/s

Table 5: Critical wind speed estimated by the third vortex frequency, f_3 ($St_3=0.438$)

4.2 Aeroelastic Response

The two-dimensional aeroelastic analysis calculates the generalized coordinate that indicates how dominant each mode is with respect to wind speed, and the displacement amplitude of the cross-section of the brimmed-diffuser shroud at certain wind speed. The result is summarized in Figs. 15-18. The peaks in the generalized coordinate for all models are in good agreement with the critical wind

speeds estimated. In all generalized coordinate curves shown in the left graphs of Figs. 15-18, the influence of the radial mode is small while the rotational mode is dominant. It is because the radial mode that behaves in the radial direction only is hardly excited by the vortex-shedding modes related to the drag force acting in the horizontal direction. Even in the original model, there are no significant peaks shown as estimated in the first natural mode in Fig. 15. On the other hand, the dominance of the rotational mode in all models means that it is more prone to induce vibration than any other model. The influence of the rotational mode is apparent in the right graph of Figs. 15-18 because the displacement amplitude at the brim tip is similar to the tendency of the rotational mode in the left graphs of Figs. 15-18. The x-direction refers to the horizontal direction, and the y-direction is perpendicular to the x-direction, which is vertical. As shown in the right graphs of Figs. 15-18, the trend of the displacement amplitude is similar to that of the generalized coordinate for the rotational mode. Thus, the most harmful vibrational mode to the structure of the brimmed-diffuser shroud is the rotational mode. Regardless of the high bending rigidity of the CFRP laminate applied to the brimmed-diffuser shroud, the rotational mode appears in all models. As mentioned in 4.1, the unidirectional CFRP support arms experience the torsion to give rise to the rotational mode, as shown in Fig. 11. Consequently, no reduction in the displacement amplitude is seen in the models with the unidirectional CFRP support arms although they have higher natural frequencies than the original model. Therefore, the high bending rigidity of the brimmed-diffuser shroud and the support arms does not directly lead to the prevention of the vortex-induced vibration in the brimmed-diffuser shroud. Also, the torsional rigidity is required to be enhanced to restrain the support arms from the oscillation to cause the rotational mode.

Figure 15: Generalized coordinate (left) and displacement amplitude (right) of WL-O

Figure 16: Generalized coordinate (left) and displacement amplitude (right) of WL-D

Figure 17: Generalized coordinate (left) and displacement amplitude (right) of WL-S

Figure 18: Generalized coordinate (left) and displacement amplitude (right) of WL-DS

5 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of CFRPs on the vortex-induced vibration in the brimmed-diffuser shroud has been investigated using the modal analysis and the aeroelastic analysis. The replacement of the aluminum alloy with CFRP in the structure of the brimmed-diffuser shroud modified its mode shapes and natural frequencies. However, that was not able to prevent the rotational mode accompanied by the oscillation of the support arms, which is the harmful vibrational mode to the vortex-induced vibration. It was because the reinforcement of the diffuser with CFRP makes the support arms relatively flexible. Hence, in order to accomplish the effective structural reinforcement against vortex-induced vibration in the brimmed-diffuser shroud, the balance of the rigidity of the diffuser and the support arms needs to be taken into account. Furthermore, the bending and the torsional rigidity of the support arm are required to be strengthened in balance.

REFERENCES

- [1] Yuji Ohya, and Takashi Karasudani, A shrouded wind turbine generating high output power with wind-lens technology, *Energies*, **3**, 2010, pp. 634-649 (<https://doi.org/10.3390/en3040634>)
- [2] Yuji Ohya, Development of a highly efficient wind turbine and its future, *Applied Mechanics Committee, JSCE*, Vol. **12**, 2009, pp. 3-11

- [3] Taeyoung Kim, Hiroto Nagai, Nobuhide Uda, and Yuji Ohya, Vortex-induced vibration analysis of a brimmed-diffuser shroud of a wind turbine, *Kyushu University - KAIST Symposium on Aerospace Engineering, Fukuoka Japan, December 7-9, 2017*, pp. 1-4
- [4] Peter A. Irwin, Bluff body aerodynamics in wind engineering. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, **96**, 2008, pp. 701-712 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jweia.2007.06.008>)
- [5] T. Sarpkaya, A critical review of the intrinsic nature of vortex-induced vibrations. *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, **19**, 2004, pp. 389-447 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfluidstructs.2004.02.005>)
- [6] Ming Zhao, Liang Cheng, and Tongming Zhou, Numerical Simulation of Vortex-Induced Vibration of a Square Cylinder at a Low Reynolds Number, *Physics of Fluids*, **25**, 023603, 2013 (<https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4792351>)
- [7] Banafsheh Seyed-Aghazadeh, Daniel W. Carlson, and Yahya Modarres-Sadeghi. Vortex-Induced Vibration and Galloping of Prisms with Triangular Cross-Sections, *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, vol. **817**, 2017, pp. 590-618 (<https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2017.119>)
- [8] S. Komatsu, and H. Kobayashi, VORTEX-INDUCED OSCILLATION OF BLUFF CYLINDERS, *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, **6**, 1980, pp. 335-362 ([https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-6105\(80\)90010-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-6105(80)90010-0))
- [9] S. Deniz, and Th. Staubli, Oscillating Rectangular and Octagonal Profiles: Interaction of Leading-and Trailing-Edge Vortex Formation, *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, **11**, 1997, pp. 3-31 (<https://doi.org/10.1006/jfls.1996.0065>)
- [10] Taeyoung Kim, Hiroto Nagai, Nobuhide Uda, and Yuji Ohya, Influence of Structural Reinforcements in a Brimmed Diffuser for a Wind Turbine on its Mode Shapes and Vortex-Induced Vibration, *JSASS Western Branch, Fukuoka Japan, November 22, 2018*, JSASS-2018-S013
- [11] H. R. Maheri, and R. D. Adams, Vibration Properties of Structural FRP Composites, *JSME International Journal*, Series **A**, Vol. **42**, No. **3**, 1999, pp. 307-320 (<https://doi.org/10.1299/jsmea.42.307>)
- [12] D. M. De Leon, C. E. de Souza, J. S. O. Fonseca, and R. G. A. da Silva, Aeroelastic tailoring using fiber orientation and topology optimization, *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*, **46**, 2012, 663-677 (<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00158-012-0790-8>)
- [13] James M. Whitney, *Structural Analysis Of Laminated Anisotropic Plates*, Technomic Publishing Company, Inc, 1987
- [14] Hiroto Nagai, Koji Isogai, Tatsumi Fujimoto, and Toshiyuki Hayase, Experimental and numerical study of forward flight aerodynamics of insect flapping wing, *AIAA Journal*, Vol. **47**, No. **3**, 2009, pp. 730-742 (<https://doi.org/10.2514/1.39462>)
- [15] Hiroto Nagai, Koji Isogai, Masahiko Murozono, and Tsutomu Fujushiro, Investigation on structural and aerodynamic characteristics of resonant type elastic flapping wing, *ICAS2012*, **2012-9.5.3**, 2012 (http://www.icas.org/ICAS_ARCHIVE/ICAS2012/)